

Thematic DataCubes on-Demand (TheDe): Leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) for Geospatial Data Discovery and Exploitation in Earth Observation (EO)

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Abstract

Thematic DataCubes on-Demand (TheDe) aims to create a new type of data dissemination service that enables the automatic generation of thematic datacubes on demand. It integrates Earth Observation (e.g., Copernicus products) and other geospatial environmental data with Large Language Models (LLMs) and agentic components, transforming diverse datasets into accessible, meaningful information for both domain experts and a broader audience.

Keywords: Agentic LLMs, On-Demand Data-Cubes, Earth Observation

1. Introduction

The combined use of satellite data, model output, and other geospatial information layers requires a wide set of multidisciplinary skills that are often hard to find all together among scientists who are more educated in e.g. understanding, managing, or responding to natural and climate change-connected events. On these premises, there is a need to develop tools that enable non-specialists to access and exploit the increasing capabilities emerging from the fusion of different Earth Observation (EO)-based and other geospatial data.

Building upon the need for accessible tools that facilitate the exploration and exploitation of diverse Earth Observation (EO) and geospatial data sources, this work proposes a new automated dissemination service named Thematic DataCubes on-Demand (TheDe). TheDe aims to fill this gap by enabling users to formulate concrete data requests through natural language queries and automatically retrieve thematic DataCubes generated according to their specific requirements.

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At its current stage of development, the project focuses on the design phase of TheDe, emphasizing three key aspects:

- The added value of introducing a technology like TheDe for improving data accessibility and thematic integration.
- The adoption of an agentic approach to guide the development of intelligent, task-oriented components within the system.
- The identification and definition of applications and use cases in collaboration with real-world stakeholders, ensuring the relevance and applicability of TheDe to practical Earth Observation scenarios.

2. Methodology

2.1. Review Analysis of the State of the Art and Assessing the Gaps

To establish the conceptual and technical basis for TheDe, a review of recent developments in Earth Observation (EO), geospatial data infrastructures, and AI-driven data access systems was conducted. The review followed a qualitative, exploratory approach focusing on scientific publications, ESA institutional reports, and technical documentation related to thematic DataCube generation, agent-based frameworks, and large language model (LLM) integration in geospatial contexts.

The objective was to identify relevant works based on their contribution to themes such as LLM-assisted geospatial reasoning, automated data fusion, and interactive querying of EO data repositories. Notes and excerpts were systematically organized to outline emerging trends, existing limitations, and potential opportunities where TheDe could introduce innovation. The outcome of this literature phase served as the foundation for defining TheDe's functional requirements.

2.2. Developing the Conceptual Architecture

The development of the conceptual architecture for TheDe was guided by a combination of knowledge consolidation and exploratory testing. First, existing technological approaches related to data discovery, semantic interaction, and automated processing were systematically reviewed and analysed to identify transferable elements relevant to TheDe's objectives. This process drew upon prior experiences and prototypes developed in related research contexts, which served as reference models for assessing technical feasibility.

Based on this collected knowledge, a series of small-scale methodological trials were conducted to examine how different components, such as retrieval agents, orchestration mechanisms, and data transformation tools, could be generalized to operate within a unified on-demand framework. These experimental exercises were not aimed at producing an operational system but rather at evaluating the adaptability and interoperability of candidate technologies.

The insights obtained through this process enabled the formulation of a conceptual design path and highlighted the potential of an agent-based approach to support flexible, automated generation of thematic DataCubes in TheDe.

2.3. Engaging the EO Community for Use-Case Definition

To ensure that TheDe aligns with operational practices and emerging needs within the Earth Observation (EO) domain, a consultation process was conducted involving representatives from

relevant institutional, and industrial communities. The aim was to collect insights on present challenges in accessing and exploiting large-scale EO data, and to identify priority areas where TheDe could provide added value.

The interaction combined structured interviews with a questionnaire designed to gather qualitative and quantitative feedback. Participants were introduced to TheDe’s main objectives and conceptual framework, and invited to discuss its potential applications, technical requirements, and expected benefits in their respective operational contexts.

The outcomes of this process informed the identification of potential application domains and supported the definition of representative use cases that will guide the upcoming implementation and validation phases of TheDe.

3. Results

3.3. Workflow and model components

Following the exploratory design, the methodological trials and consultation activities, the conceptual formulation of TheDe has evolved into a modular system structured around six key components that collectively define the conceptual workflow of TheDe *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. The conceptual workflow of TheDe and its components interactions.

Large Language Model (LLM)

In TheDe the primary function of the LLM is semantic interpretation: extracting the contextual meaning of user inputs and expressing them in a format that components, such as agents or tools, can act upon. Beyond query interpretation, the LLM also supports the generation of descriptive text outputs, for example in documenting metadata, summarizing retrieved thematic DataCubes. Analysis of current open-source LLMs (Qwen, Llama, Mistral etc.) revealed that, within the Earth Observation (EO) domain, none demonstrated consistently superior performance unless supported by task-specific fine-tuning or retrieval-augmented strategies (Angels Balaguer et al. 2024). For this reason, TheDe will rely on the integration of existing EO-adapted LLMs instead of developing

a new model from scratch. Such models, fine-tuned or extended through RAG for EO terminology and context, provide that domain-specific reasoning and vocabulary are natively embedded. This strategy enables TheDe to build its agentic framework around a specialized LLM already optimized for interpreting EO-related queries and generating coherent, context-aware textual outputs. An example of such EO-specific models is the Earth Virtual Expert (EVE) currently being developed within ESA’s Phi-lab, which represents the type of technology TheDe aims to adopt in future implementations. In particular, on the EO and Earth Sciences benchmarks developed within the EVE project, EVE-Instruct outperforms Qwen3 and Llama4 Scout, achieving 86.12 on multi-answer MCQA versus 78.40 and 80.32, 77.73 on single-answer MCQA versus 66.36 and 71.23, and 84.70 on hallucination detection versus 81.30 and 66.08, respectively (Alex R. Atrio et al. 2026).

Agents

Agents represent the operational core that interprets the reasoning output of the LLM and transforms it into executable actions through dedicated tools, and delegated sub-agents. They embody different control strategies depending on the required level of autonomy and determinism acting as the tools orchestrator (Peilin Feng et al. 2026). Conceptually, three main types are analyzed: static, dynamic (e.g., Smolagent), and hybrid agents (e.g., LangGraph). Within TheDe’s multi-task workflow, these agent types are explored for operating in a complementary manner.

Tools

Each agent in TheDe operates through a dedicated set of tools that constitute the system’s operational layer, supporting information retrieval, management, and processing. From the state-of-the-art review, five main tool categories were identified, collection, parameter, payload check, retrieve, and download tools, each corresponding to a specific stage in the data interaction process, from discovery to access.

While existing frameworks implement these tools in different ways, TheDe will systematically explore their integration within an agentic architecture, assessing how distinct tool configurations interact with static, dynamic, and hybrid agents. This exploration, planned for the implementation phase, aims at defining best practices for combining automation, robustness, and adaptability in thematic DataCube generation.

Data-Agnostic Fusion Tool (DAFT)

The Data-Agnostic Fusion Tool (DAFT) functions as the component responsible for transforming heterogeneous datasets into harmonized thematic DataCubes. Based on the information exchanged between the LLM and the agents, DAFT performs tasks such as aggregation, reformatting, and standardization, ensuring that results ready to be downloaded.

In parallel, metadata produced during this process are re-interpreted by the LLM to generate textual descriptions that accompany each output package. Although DAFT has been previously developed and validated in other contexts, its adaptation to TheDe will extend its capabilities toward a fully integrated, on-demand workflow that supports dynamic EO data harmonization within the agentic framework.

Datasets

The initial landscape analysis identified six primary data catalogues providing diverse geospatial resources relevant for thematic DataCube generation. These include Copernicus infrastructures

such as the Climate Data Store (CDS) and Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE); cloud platforms like AWS S3 (ESA data buckets) and Google Earth Engine; and specialized providers including WorldPop, EUMETSAT, and ESA Climate Change Initiatives (CCI). Together, these catalogues cover a broad range of climate, satellite, thematic, and demographic datasets.

For each dataset, a baseline catalogue was compiled and documented through key metadata elements: dataset name, provider, potential use cases, official product references, spatial and temporal coverage and resolution, data variables, and access modalities including API endpoints and documentation.

The dataset inventory in *Table 1* represents a first step toward mapping available EO and geospatial data sources applicable to TheDe. It is designed to remain flexible and expandable, allowing new datasets to be incorporated as additional use cases and thematic requirements emerge.

Dataset	Source
SENTINEL-2 (L1C, L2A)	European Space Agency (ESA) / Copernicus https://sentiwiki.copernicus.eu/web/s2-products
SENTINEL-3 (SLSTR, OLCI, SYN)	European Space Agency (ESA) / Copernicus https://sentiwiki.copernicus.eu/web/olci-products
SENTINEL-5P TROPOMI	European Space Agency (ESA) / Copernicus https://sentiwiki.copernicus.eu/web/s5p-products
ESA CCI Soil Moisture	European Space Agency (ESA) / Climate Change Initiative (CCI) https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/satellite-soil-moisture?tab=overview
ESA World Cover	European Space Agency (ESA) / Vito Remote Sensing https://esa-worldcover.org/en
World Cereal	European Space Agency (ESA) https://esa-worldcereal.org/en/worldcereal-products
Copernicus DEM (Digital Elevation Model)	European Space Agency (ESA) https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/explore-data/data-collections/copernicus-contributing-missions/collections-description/COP-DEM
WorldPop	WorldPop Research Group https://www.worldpop.org/datacatalog/
EUMETSAT LSA SAF	EUMETSAT https://lsa-saf.eumetsat.int/en/data/products/

Table 1. List of potential datasets with their features that TheDe shall integrate.

Archive

The Archive component of TheDe serves as a temporary repository for user-specific data and intermediate results. It supports iterative processing by preserving previously retrieved and processed data, enabling rapid access to existing results without re-executing the entire workflow pipeline. This approach improves efficiency and facilitates the scalable data retrieval workflow.

3.3. Requirements and use cases

Feedback collected from consultations with the Earth Observation (EO) community reinforced the relevance and concrete need for a system like TheDe. Participants emphasized that current approaches to thematic DataCube generation often lack automation, interpretability, and flexible access, highlighting TheDe’s potential to fill this methodological gap.

The requirements emerging from this dialogue can be grouped into several key outlooks. Stakeholders expressed the preference for pre-defined constraints guiding dataset selection to ensure consistency and reliability. Across all groups, the importance of transparent model feedback and explainability was strongly noted requesting that the system explicitly list and describe the datasets identified and used in each process. This shall lead to a careful development and choice of the agents integrated into TheDe.

Concerning data exploitation, participants suggested multiple access options including GeoServer interfaces, Jupyter notebooks, online storage environments, and web-based visualization tools, while some favored direct data download for offline use. Preferences regarding data format and level of aggregation appeared use-case specific, ranging from raw satellite data to administratively aggregated indicators. The DAFT shall adapt for the generation of such outputs.

Overall, the diversity of these requirements allows TheDe to refer to a broad scope of applications as the thematic examples in Table 2.

Use Case	Example query	Example datasets	Example outputs
Wildfire	Provide data to study wildfires in continental Africa from 2019 onward, prioritizing Copernicus datasets.	Copernicus Fire Radiative Power products, temperature and land-surface datasets from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS).	Number and list of datasets identified, collected, and not collected, together with a GeoServer deployment hosting the curated data package.
Biomass Change (Land Cover)	Produce time-series visualizations of above-ground biomass (AGB) dynamics in Gabon from 2007 onward.	ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) data, Copernicus Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Sentinel-3 FRP, NASA datasets including MODIS, VIIRS, and GEDI variables	Interactive lists, web-based exploration tools, and development environments for spatiotemporal analysis.
Civil Security Indicators	Provide datasets to support global assessments of civil security, without specific temporal constraints.	World Settlement Footprint (WSF), NASA night-time light observations, and administrative boundary data (e.g., levels 1 and 2) for spatial aggregation.	Dataset lists, interactive exploitation tools, and aggregated indicators over selected administrative levels formatted as raster or vector data.

Table 2. Thematic applications that TheDe could face.

To address the diversity of use cases, TheDe is planned to be designed to integrate specialized user-provided LLMs and operate as an external service orchestrated by such models, enabling data discovery, access, and delivery. In this way, by simply providing natural language queries the system “LLM + TheDe” can complete the full process of the data discovery. For the currently defined applications, a representative example is the ESA open-source EO-specialized LLM, the Earth Virtual Expert (EVE) (Àlex R. Atrio et al. 2026).

Supporting different extensions requires adherence to standard technical protocols, which will be a key consideration in the development of TheDe to ensure flexibility, scalability, and broad adoption.

4. Conclusion

The first outcome of this work has been the identification of a critical gap in the current Earth Observation (EO) landscape: the absence of an integrated solution for automatic, on-demand retrieval and preparation of geospatial data. TheDe directly targets this gap, as supported from both the state-of-the-art review and feedback collected within the EO community.

Through this exploratory phase, the technological foundations required to build such a service were delineated around six core components: LLM, Agents, Tools, DAFT, Datasets, and Archive. Together form the conceptual architecture of TheDe. Their systematic integration constitutes the innovative potential of the approach proposed.

The current activities focus on a service-design strategy aimed at aligning development with actual user needs. Preliminary use cases covering wildfire monitoring, biomass-change assessment, and civil-security indicators indicate the model’s applicability to real-world scenarios.

From a technical perspective, TheDe is planned to become one of the first adopters of the ESA open-source EO-specialized LLM, the Earth Virtual Expert (EVE), marking an important step toward operationalizing AI-supported geospatial data exploitation. Moreover, TheDe aims to operate as external server interoperable with user-provided LLMs and other existing LLM-based workflows.

In conclusion, a next implementation phase should consolidate these results into a functional prototype, advancing toward an adaptive and explainable system for thematic DataCube generation on demand.

References

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